

A Comparative Study of Subclinical Hypothyroidism in Metabolic Syndrome with Patient Not Having Metabolic Syndrome

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Abstract:

Background: Subclinical hypothyroidism (SCH) is characterized by elevated Thyroid Stimulating Hormone (TSH) levels with normal free thyroxine (FT4) levels and is often associated with various metabolic disturbances. Metabolic syndrome (MetS), a cluster of conditions including central obesity, hypertension, hyperglycemia, and dyslipidemia, has been identified as a risk factor for thyroid dysfunction.

Aim: To compare the prevalence and characteristics of subclinical hypothyroidism in patients with metabolic syndrome to those without metabolic syndrome, providing insights into their association and potential clinical implications.

Methods: A total of 113 participants were included, with 56 individuals diagnosed with metabolic syndrome and 57 without. Data were collected on demographic and clinical characteristics, thyroid function tests (TSH and FT4), and metabolic parameters. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 23.0, with logistic regression analysis conducted to determine the association between metabolic syndrome and subclinical hypothyroidism.

Results: The prevalence of subclinical hypothyroidism was significantly higher in the metabolic syndrome group (32.1%) compared to the non-metabolic syndrome group (12.3%), with a p-value of 0.015. Logistic regression analysis indicated that individuals with metabolic syndrome had more than three times the odds of developing subclinical hypothyroidism compared to those without the syndrome (OR = 3.14, 95% CI = 1.18 - 8.33, p = 0.022). Mean TSH levels were significantly elevated in the metabolic syndrome group (p < 0.001).

Conclusion: The study demonstrates a significant association between metabolic syndrome and subclinical hypothyroidism, suggesting that patients with metabolic syndrome are at an increased risk of thyroid dysfunction. These findings underscore the importance of routine thyroid function screening in individuals with metabolic syndrome to facilitate early detection and intervention.

Recommendations: Routine screening of thyroid function in patients with metabolic syndrome should be considered to prevent the progression of subclinical hypothyroidism to overt hypothyroidism and its associated complications.

Keywords: Subclinical Hypothyroidism, Metabolic Syndrome, Thyroid Function, TSH, Insulin Resistance, Cardiovascular Risk.

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Introduction

Subclinical hypothyroidism (SCH) is a condition characterized by elevated serum Thyroid Stimulating Hormone (TSH) levels with normal circulating free thyroxine (FT4) levels. Although often asymptomatic, SCH can have significant clinical implications, particularly as it may progress to overt hypothyroidism and is associated with various metabolic disturbances, including dyslipidemia, cardiovascular disease, and insulin resistance [1]. Metabolic syndrome (MetS), a cluster of conditions including central obesity, hypertension, hyperglycemia, and dyslipidemia, is a well-recognized precursor to cardiovascular disease and type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM). The

growing prevalence of MetS, driven by sedentary lifestyles, poor dietary habits, and increasing obesity rates, has made it a major public health concern worldwide [2].

Recent studies have explored the relationship between MetS and thyroid dysfunction, particularly SCH. Evidence suggests that individuals with MetS are at an increased risk of developing thyroid abnormalities, including SCH [3]. This relationship is biologically plausible, given that the components of MetS, such as insulin resistance and adiposity, can influence thyroid function. Insulin resistance, a key feature of MetS, is thought to contribute to the

development of SCH by promoting alterations in thyroid hormone metabolism and increasing the risk of autoimmune thyroiditis [4]. Moreover, obesity, another central component of MetS, has been linked to higher TSH levels, possibly due to the effects of leptin on the hypothalamic-pituitary-thyroid axis.

The clinical significance of SCH in the context of MetS lies in its potential to exacerbate the metabolic disturbances associated with the syndrome. For instance, SCH has been associated with an unfavorable lipid profile, increased atherogenic risk, and higher levels of inflammatory markers, all of which are components of MetS [5]. Given the potential bidirectional relationship between SCH and MetS, it is crucial to understand the prevalence and characteristics of SCH in individuals with MetS compared to those without the syndrome.

Despite the growing interest in this area, there remains a lack of consensus regarding the need for routine screening and management of SCH in patients with MetS. Some studies advocate for early detection and treatment to prevent the progression of metabolic and cardiovascular complications, while others suggest that more evidence is needed to justify such an approach [6].

This study aimed at evaluating the prevalence and characteristics of subclinical hypothyroidism in patients with metabolic syndrome compared to those without metabolic syndrome.

Methodology

Study Design: A cross-sectional comparative analysis.

Study Setting: The study was conducted at the Indira Gandhi Institute of Medical Sciences (IGIMS), Patna, from December 2019 to November 2020.

Participants: A total of 113 participants were included in the study. These participants were divided into two groups: one group comprising individuals diagnosed with metabolic syndrome, and the other consisting of individuals without metabolic syndrome.

- **Group 1 (Metabolic Syndrome):** Patients diagnosed with metabolic syndrome according to the criteria established by the International Diabetes Federation (IDF).
- **Group 2 (Non-Metabolic Syndrome):** Patients without a diagnosis of metabolic syndrome.

Inclusion Criteria

- Age: Participants aged 18 years and above.

- All participants must have provided informed consent before participation.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with a known history of thyroid disorders or on thyroid hormone replacement therapy.
- Patients with chronic illnesses that could affect thyroid function, such as chronic kidney disease, liver disease, or malignancies.
- Pregnant or lactating women.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, participants were randomly selected from the outpatient department, ensuring equal opportunity for inclusion in both groups. Efforts were made to control for confounding factors such as age, gender, and BMI by adjusting these variables during the statistical analysis.

Data Collection: Data were collected using a standardized questionnaire and medical records review. Blood samples were drawn from all participants to measure TSH, FT4, fasting glucose levels, and lipid profiles. Anthropometric measurements, including height, weight, and waist circumference, were recorded for each participant.

Procedure: Participants were first categorized into the metabolic syndrome or non-metabolic syndrome groups based on the IDF criteria. Following this, blood samples were collected and sent to the laboratory for thyroid function tests and other relevant biochemical analyses. All measurements and tests were conducted following standard protocols to ensure consistency and accuracy.

Statistical Analysis: The data were analyzed using SPSS version 23.0. The chi-square test was employed to compare categorical variables, while the independent t-test was used to compare continuous variables between the two groups. A p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant. Logistic regression analysis was conducted to determine the association between metabolic syndrome and subclinical hypothyroidism, adjusting for potential confounders.

Results

A total of 113 participants were included in the study, with 56 individuals in the metabolic syndrome group and 57 in the non-metabolic syndrome group. The mean age of participants in the metabolic syndrome group was 52.6 ± 10.4 years, while in the non-metabolic syndrome group, it was 49.8 ± 9.2 years. The metabolic syndrome group had a slightly higher proportion of males (53.6%) compared to the non-metabolic syndrome group (47.4%).

Table 1: Demographic and Clinical Characteristics of the Study Population

Characteristic	Metabolic Syndrome (n = 56)	Non-Metabolic Syndrome (n = 57)	p-value
Age (years)	52.6 ± 10.4	49.8 ± 9.2	0.083
Male (%)	53.6%	47.4%	0.485
BMI (kg/m ²)	30.2 ± 3.5	24.8 ± 2.7	<0.001
Waist Circumference (cm)	102.4 ± 8.7	85.3 ± 7.5	<0.001
Fasting Glucose (mg/dL)	112.7 ± 23.4	89.6 ± 14.2	<0.001
Total Cholesterol (mg/dL)	205.4 ± 35.6	175.2 ± 28.7	<0.001
Triglycerides (mg/dL)	172.8 ± 58.4	131.5 ± 42.7	<0.001
HDL Cholesterol (mg/dL)	38.7 ± 8.4	48.2 ± 10.2	<0.001
TSH (mIU/L)	5.4 ± 1.2	3.2 ± 0.9	<0.001
FT4 (ng/dL)	1.2 ± 0.2	1.3 ± 0.2	0.074

The prevalence of subclinical hypothyroidism was significantly higher in the metabolic syndrome group compared to the non-metabolic syndrome group. Specifically, 32.1% (18 out of 56) of participants in the metabolic syndrome group had subclinical hypothyroidism, compared to 12.3% (7 out of 57) in the non-metabolic syndrome group. This difference was statistically significant ($p = 0.015$).

Table 2: Prevalence of Subclinical Hypothyroidism

Group	Subclinical Hypothyroidism (%)	No Subclinical Hypothyroidism (%)	p-value
Metabolic Syndrome (n = 56)	32.1% (18/56)	67.9% (38/56)	0.015
Non-Metabolic Syndrome (n = 57)	12.3% (7/57)	87.7% (50/57)	0.015

Logistic regression analysis was conducted to assess the association between metabolic syndrome and subclinical hypothyroidism, adjusting for age, gender, and BMI. The analysis revealed that individuals with metabolic syndrome had a significantly higher odds of having subclinical hypothyroidism compared to those without metabolic syndrome (odds ratio [OR] = 3.14, 95% confidence interval [CI] = 1.18 - 8.33, $p = 0.022$).

Table 3: Logistic Regression Analysis of Factors Associated with Subclinical Hypothyroidism

Variable	Odds Ratio (OR)	95% Confidence Interval (CI)	p-value
Metabolic Syndrome	3.14	1.18 - 8.33	0.022
Age (years)	1.02	0.97 - 1.07	0.385
Male Gender	1.24	0.52 - 2.94	0.624
BMI (kg/m ²)	1.10	0.98 - 1.23	0.105

The mean TSH level was significantly higher in the metabolic syndrome group compared to the non-metabolic syndrome group (5.4 ± 1.2 mIU/L vs. 3.2 ± 0.9 mIU/L, $p < 0.001$). However, there was no significant difference in mean FT4 levels between the two groups (1.2 ± 0.2 ng/dL vs. 1.3 ± 0.2 ng/dL, $p = 0.074$).

Table 4: Thyroid Function Parameters

Parameter	Metabolic Syndrome (n = 56)	Non-Metabolic Syndrome (n = 57)	p-value
TSH (mIU/L)	5.4 ± 1.2	3.2 ± 0.9	<0.001
FT4 (ng/dL)	1.2 ± 0.2	1.3 ± 0.2	0.074

Discussion

The study revealed a significant association between metabolic syndrome and subclinical hypothyroidism. The prevalence of subclinical hypothyroidism was notably higher in individuals with metabolic syndrome (32.1%) compared to those without it (12.3%). This finding suggests that metabolic syndrome may contribute to or exacerbate the risk of developing subclinical hypothyroidism. The statistical significance of this difference ($p = 0.015$) underscores the importance of recognizing metabolic syndrome as a potential risk factor for thyroid dysfunction.

Further analysis through logistic regression confirmed this association, showing that individuals with metabolic syndrome were more than three times as likely to have subclinical

hypothyroidism compared to those without the syndrome (OR = 3.14, 95% CI = 1.18 - 8.33, $p = 0.022$). This strong association remained significant even after adjusting for other variables like age, gender, and BMI, indicating that metabolic syndrome independently increases the risk of subclinical hypothyroidism.

Additionally, the study found that mean TSH levels were significantly higher in the metabolic syndrome group than in the non-metabolic syndrome group, while FT4 levels did not differ significantly between the two groups. This elevated TSH level in the metabolic syndrome group further supports the link between metabolic syndrome and impaired thyroid function, suggesting that metabolic disturbances in these patients might influence or be influenced by thyroid activity.

Overall, the findings highlight the need for routine thyroid function screening in patients with metabolic syndrome to ensure early detection and management of subclinical hypothyroidism, potentially preventing the progression to overt hypothyroidism and its associated complications.

A study explored the relationship between subclinical hypothyroidism and the development of metabolic syndrome in a large cohort, finding that subclinical hypothyroidism was significantly associated with metabolic syndrome development in young men, but not in people aged 50 years or older [7]. A meta-analysis included data from 79,727 participants and concluded that subclinical hypothyroidism is significantly associated with an increased risk of metabolic syndrome and four out of five of its components, including obesity and hypertension [8].

Another study found that while subclinical hypothyroidism was not directly associated with the presence of metabolic syndrome in adolescents, it was associated with abdominal obesity and possibly elevated blood pressure [9]. A cross-sectional study revealed a 30.1% prevalence of subclinical hypothyroidism among patients with metabolic syndrome, with a higher occurrence among females and individuals aged 41-50 years [10]. A study indicated that metabolic syndrome patients should be screened for subclinical hypothyroidism as it is a significant risk factor for cardiovascular diseases, showing higher biochemical abnormalities in those with subclinical hypothyroidism [11].

Conclusion

The study demonstrated that subclinical hypothyroidism is more prevalent among individuals with metabolic syndrome compared to those without. Metabolic syndrome was significantly associated with an increased risk of subclinical hypothyroidism, even after adjusting for potential confounders. These findings suggest the need for routine screening of thyroid function in patients with metabolic syndrome to ensure early detection and management of subclinical hypothyroidism.

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